

Factors Affecting Mental Health and Wellbeing: A Review Paper

Dr. Bhawna Pradhan

Associate Professor
T.D. B.Ed. College
Alwar, Rajasthan

Abstract:

Mental health is about how people think, feel, and behave. Mental health care professionals can help people manage conditions such as depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, addiction, and other disorders that affect their thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. Mental health can affect a person's day-to-day life, relationships, and physical health. External factors in people's lives and relationships can also contribute to their mental well-being. Stress, depression, and anxiety can affect mental health and may disrupt a person's routine.

Introduction:

According to the **World Health Organization (WHO)** “Mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community.” The WHO states that mental health is “more than the absence of mental disorders.” Good mental health is about managing active conditions and maintaining wellness and happiness.

The organization also emphasizes that preserving and restoring mental health is important at individual, community, and societal levels. In the United States, the National Alliance on Mental Illness estimates that almost 1 in 5 adults experience mental health problems each year.

Factors that affect our mental health:

- **Environment**
- **Experiences**
- **Family and upbringing**
- **Biological Factors**
- **Psychological Factors**
- **Social Factors**
- **Socio-economic factors**

These are generally categorized factors affecting mental health and wellbeing of an individual. Besides above mentioned category of factors other factors may also affect mental health and wellbeing of an individual.

Objective of the Study:

1. To identify the factors affecting mental health and wellbeing of an individual.

Methodology:

This is a research work based on the studies already carried out in the concerned field. On the basis of the review of the existing studies the researcher would try to identify the factors affecting mental health and wellbeing of an individual. To identify the factors affecting mental health of an individual, studies done on this topic in different field were taken into consideration:

Review Analysis:

The aim of the study of **Sybrein Slimmen et. al. (2022)** was to explore 1) the association of underlying stressors (academic pressure, family circumstances, side-activity pressure, and financial situation) with perceived stress and mental wellbeing, 2) whether perceived stress mediates the association between the sources of stress and mental wellbeing and 3) whether loneliness, self-esteem, personality and coping styles buffer or reinforce the impact of perceived stress on mental wellbeing. A total of 875 university students (37,2% male, 62,3% female, mean age 21,6) participated. Perceived stress had a strong negative association with mental wellbeing (unstandardized regression coefficient (b) = -.848, $p < .001$; $r = -.667$, $p < .01$), explaining 45% of the variance. Academic pressure ($b = -8.014$, $p < .01$), family pressure ($b = -3.189$, $p < .01$), side-activity pressure ($b = -3.032$, $p < .01$) and financial pressure ($b = -2.041$, $p < .01$) all had a negative impact on mental wellbeing. This effect was mediated by perceived stress, but a direct effect remained for academic pressure ($b = -3.306$, $p < .01$) and family pressure ($b = -1.130$, $p < .01$). Significant interaction effects between perceived stress and mental wellbeing were found for approach coping (low = -.93, $p < .01$; high = -.64, $p < .01$) and emotional stability (low = -.81, $p < .01$; high = -.64, $p < .01$). Perceived stress has a major impact on students' mental wellbeing. Underlying stressors were mediated by perceived stress, but direct effects were also found. To protect the mental wellbeing of students, it is urgent to reduce perceived stress, suppress underlying stressors and make students more resilient through the development of found buffers, such as approach coping.

Fiona Campbell et. al. (2022) conducted a study To identify factors associated with mental health of students in higher education. A systematic review of observational studies was done to measure factors associated with student mental wellbeing and poor mental health. Extensive searches were undertaken across five databases. Those factors most strongly and consistently associated with increased risk of developing poor mental health included students with experiences of trauma in childhood, those that identify as LGBTQ and students with autism. Factors that promote wellbeing include developing strong and supportive social networks.

Students who are prepared and able to adjust to the changes that moving into higher education presents also experience better mental health. Some behaviours that are associated with poor mental health include lack of engagement both with learning and leisure activities and poor mental health literacy.

The study of **Matsuo M et. al. (2022)** aimed to investigate the factors that affect students' mental health during the pandemic from various perspectives. The multiple logistic regression analysis indicated that increased time spent online was significantly associated with mental health ($P < .05$). Human relations and the inability to meet/talk with friends trended toward a significant association with mental health ($P < .1$). The students who were not stressed about the increased time spent online were at a risk of low mental health. The students who appreciated interacting with others experienced more stress during the lockdown. To reduce students' stress on online days, teachers should devise a lecture style with frequent breaks and introduce active learning. The findings of this study will contribute to addressing students' low mental health and reducing their stress during the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic.

The research work of **Chen, Wenen et. al. (2020)** focuses on factors affecting the mental health of college students in the information network society. Results show that the quality of external Internet platforms and the quality of internal electronic health literacy have a significantly positive impact on the online health information searching behavior of college students; electronic health literacy and online mental health information seeking behavior have significantly direct positive effects on college students' mental health. Further, online health information searching behavior has a significant mediating effect between Internet platform quality, electronic health literacy, and college students' mental health.

The study of **Zeenat Ismail and Neshmia Shujaat (2018)** explores the relationship of five variables commonly associated with mental wellbeing. The variables include perceived social support, family demands, socioeconomic status, gender and educational background. Mental well-being comprises of two subcomponents i.e. stress and depression and poor mental well-being is indicated by high scores on stress and depression and vice versa. Independent T tests revealed that males ($M=20.45$, $SD=3.22$, $t(206) = 6.92$) compared to females ($M=16.92$, $SD= 4.09$) perceived greater social support, especially from their friends. Females ($M= 17.54$, $SD= 4.84$) experienced greater family demands than males ($M= 14.92$, $SD=3.70$). Females also reported higher scores on depression ($M=14.37$, $SD= 6.45$) with a moderate effect size ($\eta^2=0.06$), thereby suggesting a link between family demands and depression. Students from higher socioeconomic groups and non-mainstream educational backgrounds like the social sciences reported greater scores on stress and depression.

Travasso, S.M. (2014) examined the factors that affect their mental health at home and work. Researchers studied the relationship between work, caring for family, spousal support, stress relief strategies and mental health amongst forty eight low-income working mothers residing in urban slums across Bangalore, India. Researchers found evidence of extreme depression, including suicidal ideation and attempted suicide. Women who have an alcoholic and/or abusive

husband, experience intimate partner violence, are raising children with special needs, and lack adequate support for child care appear to be more susceptible to severe and prolonged periods of depression and suicide attempts. Factors that pointed towards reduced anxiety and depression were social support from family, friends and colleagues and fulfilment from work.

Aim of the study of **Naisi Abdul-Kazem et. al. (2009)** is to investigate the simple and multiple relationships between role ambiguity, role conflict, role overload and mental health considering the moderating role of type A personality and sense of coherence. Research results revealed that there is a significant relation between role ambiguity and mental health deficiency, but no one was found between role conflict and role overload and mental health deficiency; nevertheless, higher correlation level between role stressors and mental Health deficiency in low-level sense of coherence in comparison with high-level sense of coherence personnel was found. Also, a higher multiple correlations between role stressors and MH deficiency in personnel having further type A personality in comparison with personnel having not as much of mentioned group's type A personality was observed.

Findings:

On the basis of review analysis done above, findings have been mentioned below:

Mental health is negatively affected by following

1. Perceived stress
2. Academic pressure
3. Family pressure
4. Financial Pressure
5. Side-Activity Pressure
6. Experiences of trauma in childhood
7. lack of engagement both with learning and leisure activities.
8. Poor mental health literacy.
9. More than required time spent online
10. Socio-economic status
11. Lack of adequate support for child care
12. Lack of support from family/life partner
13. Violence in family/from life partner

14. Role Ambiguity

Suggestions:

1. To protect the mental wellbeing of students, it is urgent to reduce perceived stress, suppress underlying stressors and make students more resilient through the development of found buffers, such as approach coping.
2. Everyone should must have good and positive social network.
3. Environment of the family and school should be healthy.

References:

1. **Naisi Abdul-Kazem et. al. (2009)**. Study of Factors Affecting Mental Health. October 2009, Journal of Applied Sciences 9(10). Retrieved from DOI 10.3923/jas.2009.1956.1961
2. **What is mental health (2024)**. Retrieved from <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/154543>
3. **Sybren Slimmen et. al. (2022)**. How stress-related factors affect mental wellbeing of university students : A cross-sectional study to explore the associations between stressors, perceived stress, and mental wellbeing. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9639818/>
4. **Fiona Campbell et. al. (2022)**. Factors that influence mental health of university and college students in the UK: a systematic review. BMC Public Health 22, 1778 (2022). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-13943-x>
5. **Ismail, Z., & Shujaat, N. (2018)**. Factors Affecting the Mental Well-Being of Undergraduate Students in Karachi. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 5(3). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.14738/assrj.53.3704>
6. **Matsuo M, Sesoko S, Kosa A, Noda S, Koura S, Miyabara H, Higuchi T (2022)**. Factors affecting the mental health of medical students during the COVID-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional study. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2022 Nov 25;101(47):e31897. Retrieved from doi: 10.1097/MD.000000 0000031897.
7. **Chen, Wenen, Qian Zheng, Changyong Liang, Yuguang Xie, and Dongxiao Gu. (2020)**. Factors Influencing College Students' Mental Health Promotion: The Mediating Effect of Online Mental Health Information Seeking. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17, no. 13: 4783. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134783>
8. **Travasso, S.M., Rajaraman, D. & Heymann, S.J. (2014)**. A qualitative study of factors affecting mental health amongst low-income working mothers in Bangalore, India. *BMC Women's Health* 14, 22 (2014). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6874-14-22>